

Theoretical Studies of Some Non-benzenoid Hydrocarbons VI. Benzoderivatives of Aceheptylene, Azupyrene and Dicyclohepta [cd, gh] Pentalene

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Benzoderivatives of aceheptylene, azupyrene and dicyclohepta[cd, gh] pentalene have been studied using a self-consistent field method within the zero differential overlap approximation. Ground state properties and $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ transitions have been predicted and compared with experimental results where available.

ACEHEPTYLENE, azupyrene and dicyclohepta [cd, gh] pentalene are interesting molecules to synthetic as well as to the theoretical chemists. Recently benzoderivatives of aceheptylene¹ and azupyrene^{2a} have been synthesized and some of them also have been theoretically studied^{2b}. In this paper we would like to report the results of our calculations on some benzoderivatives of aceheptylene, azupyrene and dicyclohepta [cd, gh] pentalene (Fig. 1). using a self-consistent field approach similar to that of Pariser and Parr³, and Pople⁴. The molecules 2, 4 and 5 have been synthesized. However, a search in the literature reveals that the other molecules have not yet been synthesized. The aim of this paper is also to predict the stability of these molecules.

Method and Parameter :

The method of calculation is well known and has been described elsewhere⁵. The mode of evaluation of important integrals were also described in our previous paper⁶. The resonance integrals, β , for bonded atoms were calculated by the method of Lo and Whitehead⁷, Chung and Dewar⁸, Dewar and Harget⁹ and Yamaguchi *et al*¹⁰ designated here as SCF(a), SCF(b), SCF(c) and SCF(d) methods respectively. For the evaluation of these integrals regular planar geometry for these molecules with bond length 1.4 (Å) as far as possible was assumed (Fig. 1).

The first three methods for the evaluation of the β integral were proposed for the study of the ground state properties of the conjugated systems and the last one for the study of $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectral transitions. But we^{6,11,12} have seen that using these values of β integral proposed by Lo and Whitehead⁷ and Dewar *et al*^{8,9}, the $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra could also be predicted with reasonably good accuracy and comparable to those predicted by the SCF(d) method.

Results and Discussion

Resonance stabilization :

Table 1 contains the heat of atomization and π -bond energy calculated by the SCF(a), SCF(b) and SCF(c) methods. Table 2. contains the resonance

TABLE 1—HEAT OF ATOMIZATION, ΔH_a (eV)
AND π -BOND ENERGY, $E_{\pi \times b}$ (eV)

Mole- cule	Heat of atomization			π -bond energy		
	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)
1	155.755	156.124	156.247	26.428	25.417	25.103
2	155.768	156.800		26.442	25.592	
3	155.704	155.967	156.239	26.378	25.260	25.134
4	155.748	156.310	156.470	26.421	25.603	25.198
5	170.592	170.295	170.938	29.154	28.970	28.133
6	204.124	208.896	204.547	35.474	35.243	34.069
7	170.309	169.705	170.585	28.141	28.381	28.123
8	204.335	202.694	203.668	33.670	34.140	33.957

energy, E_R calculated by these methods and by the methods of Dewar and de Llano¹³ and Hess and Schaad¹⁴ along with the resonance energy per carbon-carbon bond, $E_R/C-C$ and resonance energy per π -electron, E_R/π (for Hess and Schaad's method only). The values of $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π of parent hydrocarbons have also been included in the Table 2 to see the effect of fusion of benzene nucleus in them. The parent hydrocarbons are completely non-benzenoid whereas the present hydrocarbons belong to semibenzenoid¹⁵ systems. The $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π values¹⁵ of aromatic semibenzenoid compounds are higher than those of aromatic non-benzenoid systems. The introduction of benzene nucleus to the parent hydrocarbons has increased the $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π (Table 2) of the present systems. But only in the case of azupyrene the successive introduction of benzene nucleus has increased the $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π suggesting that molecule 6 is more stable than molecule 5. From the values $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π it is clear that the molecules 1 and 3 are almost equally

TABLE 2—RESONANCE ENERGY, E_R (eV)
RESONANCE ENERGY PER CARBON-CARBON BOND AND E_R/π

Molecule	Resonance Energy				Resonance Energy per C—C bond				(d)	
	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)	(a)	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)	(a)	$E_R(\beta)$	E_R/π
ACEHEPTYLENE(c)					0.256	0.228	0.027	0.050		0.016
1	5.137	5.361	1.181	0.466	0.245	0.255	0.056	0.022	0.402	0.022
2	5.150	5.536	1.414 ^(b)	0.479	0.245	0.264	0.067 ^(b)	0.028	0.502 ^(b)	0.028 ^(b)
3	5.086	5.204	1.174	0.415	0.242	0.248	0.056	0.020	0.369	0.021
4	5.130	5.547	1.405	0.459	0.244	0.264	0.067	0.022	0.504	0.028
AZUPYRENE(c)					0.256	0.249	0.048	0.030		0.022
5	6.547	6.977	1.636	1.065	0.273	0.291	0.068	0.044	0.576	0.029
6	8.264	8.819	2.282	1.597	0.285	0.304	0.079	0.055	0.778	0.032
DICYCLOHEPTA (cd,gh)PENTALENE (c)					0.246	0.245	0.044	0.019		0.021
7	6.264	6.389	1.283	0.782	0.261	0.266	0.053	0.033	0.467	0.023
8	7.474	7.716	1.403	0.808	0.258	0.266	0.048	0.028	0.588	0.025

(a) Using the method of Dewar and de Llano (Ref. 13); (b) Ref. 2(b); (c) Ref. 15; (d) Hess and Schaad method (Ref. 14).

stable and the same conclusion can also be drawn for the molecules 7 and 8. However, it is clear from the Table that the molecule 2 is definitely more stable than the other benzoaceptylenes. Although the method of Dewar and de Llano predicts that the molecule 4 is less stable than the molecule 2, the methods of Dewar and Harget, and Hess and Schaad suggest that they are equally stable. Only molecules 2 and 4 have been synthesized among the benzoaceptylenes. It should be pointed out that for aromatic semibenzenoid systems the values of $E_R/C-C$ and E_R/π lie between 0.07 to 0.105 (Dewar and Harget method)¹⁵, 0.052 to 0.077 (Dewar and de Llano method)¹⁶ and 0.032 to 0.039 (Hess and Schaad method)¹⁵. Hence only molecule 6 is aromatic and all other molecules are not. The methods mentioned above are better than the SCF(a) and SCF(b) methods in predicting the aromaticity and stability of the molecules and according to the methods¹⁵ [SCF(a) and SCF(b)] the molecules 5 and 6 would be aromatic and others are not. However, the molecule 6 has not yet been synthesized and it is hoped that synthesis of it would be possible in the near future.

Reactivity :

Table 3 contains the highest and lowest centre of charge density, most probable centre of electrophilic, nucleophilic, dienophilic attack, and calculated value of π -dipolement. All the methods agree in predicting the most probable centre of electrophilic (except for the molecules 1, 2 and 4) nucleophilic and dienophilic attack for these molecules. For lack of experimental data the results cannot be compared with experimental ones.

Bond Length :

In all these molecules except molecules bond length in the benzene ring has ar 8 the character and the bond length lies between 1omatic 1.417 (Å) for the molecules 1 to 6 and for m.382 to 7 the length is 1.374 to 1.424 (Å). In aolecule molecules except molecule 1 peripheral bond II these predicted by these methods are of two types :lengths

One is aromatic and the other polyolefinic. However, SCF(c) method is less effective than the other methods in this respect. Hence any definition of aromaticity based on the global π -electron properties such as delocalization energy, magnetic property or the standard deviation of bond length¹⁴ is inadequate for these type of molecules.

Ionization Potential and Electron Affinity :

Highest occupied orbital energy and lowest unoccupied orbital energy may be approximated to be equal to the ionization potential^{17a} (IP) and electron affinity (EA) respectively. But it has been commonly observed^{17b} that the values obtained by this method are 1 or 2 eV too high. Hence we have used the following relations for the calculation of ionization potential and electron affinity.

$$IP = -(E_1 + C)eV \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$E_A = -(E_1 + D)eV \quad \dots (2)$$

where E_i and E_j are the highest occupied and lowest unoccupied orbital energy. For SCF(a), SCF(b), SCF(c) and SCF(d) the values of C are 1.29, 1.28, 1.88¹⁸ and 1.06¹⁹ respectively and the values of D for these methods are also 1.49, 1.50, 1.28 and 1.90¹⁹ respectively. For the SCF(a) and SCF(b) methods the values of C are the difference between the experimental ionization potential and highest occupied orbital energy of chrysene. For SCF(a-c) methods the values of D are the difference between the experimental electron affinity and lowest unoccupied orbital energy of chrysene. Table 4 contains the values of IP and EA calculated by these methods. Although the results cannot be compared with experimental ones as they are not available in the literature, still the order of accuracy can be estimated from calculations of other molecules where the experimental data are available and the results are shown in the Table 4A.

$\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ Spectra :

Tables 5 and 6 contain $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra calculated by these methods and experimental values where available. We have also included the results of

Fig. 1 Molecules studied. All bonds are equal to 1.40 Å. Regular geometry has been assumed as far as possible.

1. Benzo[*a*]aceheptylene,
2. Benzo[*d*]aceheptylene,
3. Benzo[*e*]aceheptylene,
4. Benzo[*f*]aceheptylene,
5. Benzoazapyrene,
6. Dibenzoazapyrene,
7. Benzodicyclohepta[*cd, gh*]pentalene,
8. Dibenzodicyclohepta[*cd, gh*]pentalene.

TABLE 3—REACTIVITY AND π -DIPOLE MOMENT (D)

Molecule	Method*	Charge Density		Position of Attack			π -dipole moment (D)
		Centre of		Electro- philic	Nucleo- philic	Diene- philic	
		Highest	Lowest				
1	a	16(1.142)	15(0.812)	16	15	C ₃ -C ₄	1.77
	b	16(1.160)	15(0.807)	16	15	C ₃ -C ₄	1.79
	c	18(1.089)	15(0.892)	18	15	C ₃ -C ₄	1.02
	d	7(1.094)	15(0.892)	18(1.078)	15	C ₃ -C ₄	1.93
2	a	5(1.130)	6(0.833)	5	6	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	2.12
	b	5,10(1.120)	2(0.832)	5	6(0.835)	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	1.92
	**c	5(1.072)	6(0.899)	5	6	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	1.65
	**d	10(1.097)	6(0.912)	8(1.069)	6	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	2.31
3	a	18(1.132)	11(0.89)	18	11	C ₃ -C ₄	2.77
	b	18(1.159)	11(0.796)	18	11	C ₃ -C ₄	1.59
	c	18(1.088)	11(0.877)	18	11	C ₃ -C ₄	0.95
	d	18(1.082)	11(0.870)	18	11	C ₃ -C ₄	1.51
4	a	3(1.139)	6(0.823)	3	6	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	2.10
	b	3(1.124)	2(0.824)	3	6(0.828)	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	2.02
	c	10(1.084)	2(0.865)	5(1.077)	6(0.892)	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	1.79
	d	10(1.096)	6(0.908)	8(1.070)	6	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	2.62
5	a	16(1.117)	4(0.858)	16	4	C ₁₉ -C ₂₀	0.10
	b	16(1.132)	4(0.825)	16	4	C ₁₉ -C ₂₀	0.05
	c	16(1.112)	1(0.848)	16	4(0.854)	C ₄ -C ₅	0.83
	d	3(1.081)	1(0.897)	16(1.038)	4(0.913)	C ₄ -C ₅	0.89
6	a	5(1.129)	4(0.852)	5	4	C ₉ -C ₁₀	0.04
	b	5(1.142)	4(0.820)	5	4	C ₉ -C ₁₀	0.01
	c	4(1.143)	4(0.821)	5	4	C ₉ -C ₁₀	0
	d	3(1.078)	1(0.900)	5(1.047)	4(0.905)	C ₉ -C ₁₀	0
7	a	4(1.136)	5(0.915)	4	6(0.962)	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	1.24
	b	4(1.149)	5(0.919)	4	6(0.955)	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	1.38
	c	4(1.089)	5(0.951)	4	6(0.955)	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	1.94
	d	1(1.091)	6(0.943)	4(1.089)	6	C ₁₇ -C ₁₈	2.26
8	a	4(1.136)	3(0.926)	4	6(0.969)	C ₉ -C ₉	0
	b	4(1.151)	3(0.927)	4	6(0.963)	C ₉ -C ₉	0
	c	4(1.145)	3(0.918)	4	6(0.970)	C ₉ -C ₉	0
	d	4(1.095)	6(0.957)	4	6	C ₉ -C ₉	0

* a, b, c and d represent SCF(a), SCF(b), SCF(c) and SCF(d) respectively.

** Ref. 2(b).

TABLE 4—IONIZATION POTENTIAL (eV) AND ELECTRON AFFINITY (eV)

Molecule	Ionization Potential				Electron Affinity			
	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)	SCF(d)	SCF(a)	SCF(b)	SCF(c)	SCF(d)
1	7.02	6.97	6.71	6.64	1.01	0.97	0.89	1.24
2	7.25	7.31	7.05	7.06	1.16	1.00	1.03	1.25
3	7.19	7.09	6.71	6.87	0.15	0.12	1.00	1.27
4	7.23	7.27	7.00	6.98	1.02	0.93	1.04	1.22
5	7.25	7.31	6.81	6.93	0.61	0.82	0.98	1.11
6	6.98	7.05	6.47	6.63	0.87	0.94	1.16	1.25
7	7.35	7.24	7.09	7.08	1.12	1.19	1.17	1.20
8	6.92	6.81	6.48	6.62	1.33	1.40	1.39	1.38

TABLE—4A

Comparison between calculated and experimental values of ionization potential* and electron affinity of some non-benzenoid hydrocarbons

Molecule	Method	Ionization potential (eV)		Electron affinity	
		Calc. (Ref. 12 and 21)	Obs.	Calc. (Ref. 12 and 21)	Obs.
Azulene	a	7.54	7.43 (Ref. 22)	0.68	0.656 (Ref. 23)
	b	7.51		0.89	
	c	7.23		0.88	
	d	7.47		1.03	
Aconaphthylone	a	8.18	8.02 (Ref. 22)	0.90	0.88 (Ref. 24)
	b	8.18		0.89	
	c	8.13		0.89	
	d	8.28		0.95	
Eluoranthene	a	7.84	7.80 (Ref. 22)	0.61	0.63 (Ref. 25)
	b	7.84		0.66	0.82 (Ref. 24)
	c	7.78		0.67	
	d	7.99		0.83	
Indene (1,2,3-cd) fluoranthene	a			1.25	(e) 1.42
	b			1.24	
	c			1.17	
	d			1.33	
Pyracylene	a			1.36	1.55 (Ref. 26)
	b			1.41	
	c			1.24	
	d			1.43	

a, b, c and d represent the SCF(a), SCF(b), SCF(c) and SCF(d) methods respectively.

(e) Predicted from the half-wave reduction potential determined by Bergman (Ref. 27). The half-wave reduction potential of Bergman has been lowered by 0.52 volts (Ref. 23).

* The value of 'C' in equation 1 is the difference between highest occupied orbital energy and experimental ionization potential of some standard molecules (benzenoid systems). Standard molecules depend on the size of the molecules.

The value of 'D' in eqn. 2 is difference between the lowest unoccupied orbital energy and experimental value of electron affinity of some standard substance as stated in the case of IP.

configuration interaction(CI) calculation in the Tables. The vectors and integrals obtained at the end of SCF(d) method is utilized in the CI procedure and all single excitations were included. The oscillator strengths were also included in the Tables and they were obtained from the relation²⁰.

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \bar{\nu} \mu^2 \dots (3)$$

where $\bar{\nu}$ is the transition energy in cm^{-1} and μ is the dipole length for the corresponding transition in \AA . For molecules 2 and 4 the present results are in very good agreement with experiment and comparable to other theoretical results where available. However, for molecule 5 the results obtained from CI calculation are also in very good agreement with experiment. Apart from the lowest transitions for this

molecule the correlation between the SCF methods and the experiment is good. The standard deviation (σ) for those methods which have point-to-point correlation with experimental spectra is also included in the Tables. From the Tables it is clear that in general spectral transitions predicted by the CI method is better than those predicted by the SCF methods. In most cases where the experimental spectra are available there is not only reasonable agreement for the transition energies but also a definite, if rough, agreement in the trends followed by the intensities. However, there are some exceptions found specially in the SCF(c) method. Since experimental data are not available polarization could not be given.

TABLE 5- $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ TRANSITION ENERGIES (ΔE , eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH (f).

Molecule	Experiment		Sym	SCF(a)		SCF(b)		SCF(c)		SCF(d)		CI	
	ΔE	$\log \epsilon$		ΔE	f								
1			B ₂	1.30	0.02	1.27	0.02	1.94	0.08	1.27	0.04	1.11	0.011
			B ₂	3.28	0.91	3.00	0.81	3.37	0.86	3.10	0.99	2.77	0.194
			A ₁	3.64	0.14	3.67	0.16	3.92	0.26	3.53	0.25	3.52	0.238
			B ₂	4.21	0.27	4.24	0.25	4.53	0.23	3.95	0.25	4.10	0.291
			A ₁	4.37	0.62	4.17	0.59	4.59	0.43	4.27	0.55	4.19	0.438
			B ₂	4.86	0.44	4.78	0.51	5.16	0.27	4.89	0.36	4.82	0.737
			A ₁	5.22	0.47	5.12	0.47	5.22	0.51	5.12	0.51	5.11	0.686
	2				1.77	0.14	1.85	0.14			1.79	0.13	1.48
				3.08	0.31	3.20	0.25	2.37	0.21	3.22	0.28	2.66	0.026
3.12				3.89	0.27	3.90	0.35	3.55	0.41	3.95	0.45	3.19	0.162
{3.77		4.47		4.61	0.39	4.79	0.38	{4.05	0.39	{3.95	0.45	{3.85	0.644
{3.99		4.54		4.94	0.14	5.02	0.18	{4.22	0.32	{4.09	0.40	{4.02	0.451
				5.24	0.11	5.09	0.19	{4.94	0.28	{4.63	0.36	{4.40	0.376
4.64		4.66		0.063		0.110		{4.86	0.29	{4.95	0.25	4.70	1.046
5.19		4.34						5.20	0.27	{5.06	0.24	4.96	0.455
										0.1		5.11	0.013
								0.268				0.063	
3				1.80	0.09	1.72	0.09			1.73	0.08	1.49	0.009
				3.16	0.41	2.97	0.91	2.36	0.15	3.10	1.06	2.78	0.143
				3.23	0.88	3.211	0.38	3.28	0.81	3.10	0.98	3.12	0.112
				3.89	0.45	3.212	0.39	3.61	0.20	3.34	0.28	3.3	0.366
						3.82	0.39	3.63	0.58	3.88	0.37	3.72	0.440
						4.15	0.29	4.18	0.19	4.16	0.31	3.97	0.519
				4.49	0.25	4.58	0.47	4.18	0.19	4.16	0.31	4.10	0.310
				4.57	0.40	4.65	0.47	4.69	0.27	4.53	0.38	4.57	0.104
				4.84	0.44	4.91	0.16	4.93	0.34	4.86	0.14	4.60	0.284
				5.16	0.19	5.16	0.08	5.10	0.20	4.92	0.48	4.81	1.085
				5.24	0.07	5.43	0.02	5.41	0.11	5.19	0.13	5.02	0.322
				5.62	0.05	5.77	0.03	5.45	0.31	5.66	0.03	5.32	0.106
				5.99	0.14	5.93	0.08	5.86	0.14	5.85	0.19	5.60	0.188
												5.97	0.311
												6	
4	(b)			1.82	0.13	1.87	0.12	2.37	0.21	1.76	0.12	1.51	0.024
	{2.99			3.02	0.48	3.06	0.52	3.29	0.25	3.17	0.50	2.72	0
	{3.13			3.61	0.75	3.59	0.69	3.45	0.66	3.54	0.66	3.04	0.259
	3.52											3.64	0.072
	3.94			3.96	0.35	3.96	0.44	4.06	0.63	4.11	0.51	3.77	0.077
	4.32			4.28	0.54	4.38	0.46	4.40	0.28	4.30	0.45	4.02	0.100
				4.56	0.10	5.04	0.13	4.95	0.06	4.57	0.30	4.22	1.056
	4.79			5.30	0.16	5.40	0.09	5.48	0.26	5.35	0.11	4.58	0.634
	5.41			5.35	0.07							4.70	0.134
				0.130		0.122		0.122		0.104		5.35	0.573

(a) Ref. 2(b); (b) Personal communication with Prof. K. Hafner

TABLE 6—TRANSITION ENERGIES (E, eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH(F)

Molecule	Experimental		Sym.	SCF(a)		SCF(b)		SCF(c)		SCF(d)		CI	
	ΔE	$\log \epsilon$		ΔE	f	ΔE	f						
5**	2.49	3.84	A ₁									2.34	0.169
	2.56	3.98											
	3.20	4.28	A ₁	3.25	0.91	3.19	0.88	3.31	0.77	2.87	0.91	3.09	0.042
	3.56	4.06	B ₂	3.31	0.96	3.54	0.93	3.42	0.66	3.51	0.90	3.12	0.057
	3.63	4.02	B ₂	3.98	0.72	3.81	0.64	3.85	0.60	3.78	0.68	3.79	0.290
			B ₂									4.32	0.845
	4.13	4.82	A ₁	3.80	0.93	3.96	0.91	3.99	0.78	4.07	0.93	4.36	1.549
	4.71	4.88	B ₂	4.83	0.1	4.50	0.15	4.58	0.13	4.94	0.48	4.76	0.143
			B ₂	5.30	0.5	5.09	0.51	4.97	0.40			5.06	0.586
	5.23	4.81	A ₁	5.42	0.39	5.40	0.42	5.34	0.33	5.33	0.41	5.29	0.762
											0.138		
6			B _{1g}	1.63	0	1.51	0	1.44	0	1.25	0	1.10	0
			B _{2u}	3.11	1.05	3.07	1.00	3.07	0.95	2.68	1.08	2.30	0.356
			B _{2u}	3.04	1.01	3.27	0.98	3.24	0.97	3.14	0.96	2.86	0.214
			A _g	3.70	0	3.52	0	3.51	0	3.32	0	3.17	0
			B _{1u}	3.71	1.06	3.93	1.04	3.91	0.96	4.07	0.25	3.84	0.215
			B _{2u}	4.57	0.22	4.33	0.19	4.27	0.17	4.03	1.08	4.14	1.752
			B _{2u}	4.28	0.68	4.14	0.59	4.16	0.58	4.03	0.63	4.14	0.854
			B _{2u}	5.07	0.02	5.14	0.53	5.03	0.52	4.99	0.53	5.01	0.763
			B _{2u}	5.32	0.44	5.32	0.46	5.27	0.46	5.24	0.46	5.07	1.144
7			B ₂			2.19	0.01			2.29	0.01	2.13	0.002
			A ₁	2.23	0.02					2.63	0.12	2.23	0.040
			B ₂	2.92	0.16	2.97	0.54	2.95	0.07	2.94	0.57	2.69	0.161
			A ₁	3.12	1.49	3.11	1.49	2.94	0.37	3.00	1.47	1.73	0.175
			A ₁	3.12	0.54	3.67	1.11	3.76	0.80	3.67	1.11	3.53	0.384
			A ₁	4.12	0.10	3.83	0.13	3.69	1.12	3.91	0.16	4.18	2.445
			B ₂					4.80	0.11	4.65	0.10	4.61	0.007
			A ₁									5.09	0.174
											5.21	0.042	
8												2.03	0.227
			B _{1g}	2.30	0	2.32	0	2.13	0	2.31	0	2.15	0
			B _{1g}	3.15	0	2.94	0	3.32	0	2.90	0	2.77	0
			B _{2u}	3.62	0.21	3.34	0.22	3.62	0.20	3.28	0.28	3.15	0.001
			B _{1g}	4.16	0	4.12	0	4.43	0	4.00	0	3.73	0
			B _{2u}	3.44	1.44	3.53	1.45	3.51	1.36	3.48	1.47	3.76	4.456
			B _{2u}	3.92	0.54	4.22	0.56	3.84	0.56	4.17	0.54	4.01	0.081
			B _{2u}	4.63	0.02	4.55	0.02	4.88	0.02	4.46	0.01	4.27	0.197
			B _{2u}	4.97	0.49	4.94	0.50	5.20	0.49	4.82	0.42	5.01	0.007

** Experimental value from Ref. 2(a)

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